

Lead City University Journal of Pedagogical Studies (LCUJoPS)

Faculty of Education
Lead City University, Ibadan,
Oyo State, Nigeria

Vol. 1, Issue 2.
December, 2025
ISSN:3121-9039

Parenting Education in Advancing Sustainable Development through Mathematics Literacy

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Abstract

Mathematics education is a discipline which is vital to the sustainability of a nation's development, particularly due to its contributions to the training of manpower in the fundamental basics of science and technology as vital tools useful in every sphere of life. Therefore, this study through review of existing literatures sourced from online data banks and archives, further investigates the relationship of parenting education, sustainable development and mathematics literacy aimed at contributing to body of existing knowledge. The findings of this study revealed that, parents' impact on children's early mathematical abilities, which shows parents readiness in participating in their children education. But parents and educators are faced by challenges such as limited information, unsupportive attitudes, and school policies about sustainability. Thus, parenting education programmes in schools should incorporate mathematics instructions in view of sustainable development, promotional materials on mathematics education should also be made available to parents to better inform them of the significance of mathematics education and their attitude towards it, and school administrators should also formulate and implement policies in support of parenting education in view of sustainable development through the practice of mathematics.

Keywords: Literacy, Mathematics, Parenting education, Sustainable development

Introduction

The progress of any society depends to a large extent on how her educational system responds to development in a sustainable pattern. And mathematics education is a discipline which is vital to the sustainability of a nation's development, because it helps train people in the fundamentals of science and technology which is essential tools in every aspect of life, mathematics education is a discipline that is essential to a country's long-term growth (Sam-Kayode, 2017). Furthermore, sustainability is a theory, method, or practice that guides the effective use of current resources to guarantee that there are enough of them to meet present and future generations' requirements (Ozili, 2022). These resources include a range of human and material resources. In order to accomplish desired outcomes in the economic, environmental, and social domains sustainably, hence, Mathematics Education is a core aspect of science education that teaches fundamental basics of science and technology.

Man's agricultural society has been transformed into a modern one with the aid of mathematics. One may argue that mathematics has been needed for as long as people have existed. Man's drive to keep track of and count the objects around him gave rise to this. Mathematics is one of the foundational courses taught at all educational levels (Richard et al., 2024). According to Omosowon et al. (2023), the main justifications for teaching mathematics in schools are: assisting in a society's technological and socioeconomic advancement; supporting the upkeep and advancement of its political, ideological, and cultural elements; and giving people the tools they need to succeed in the various domains of education or employment, private life, social life, and civic life.

Additionally, parenting education is a conscious attempt to improve or assist parents in providing better care for their children (Encyclopedia.com, 2019). This enhances social ties, enhances parental competency, enhances parent-child interactions, enhances parental mental health and well-being, and enhances child behavior (Rothe et al., 2016). Thus, introducing mathematics literacy in parenting education programmes would contribute to the advancement of sustainable development practices and also improve children mathematics competency through parent-child interactions.

Therefore, this study through review of existing literatures would further investigate the relationship of parenting education, sustainable development and mathematics literacy – it explores how parenting education influence children early mathematics skills, parenting education programs and associated barriers to parents and teachers in teaching mathematics.

Understanding Sustainable Development

The most commonly used definition of sustainable development is found in the 1987 Bruntland Commission (formerly the World Commission on Environment and Development, or WCED) report, "Our Common Future," which attempted to connect the concerns of environmental stability and economic development. It states that "Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (Bienia, 2019). This definition of sustainable development offers a framework for integrating environmental laws and policies with developmental methods, with the primary goal of guaranteeing economic progression and progress while maintaining the long-term sustainability of the environment. Sustainable development's ultimate goal is long-term economic and environmental stability at the same time, which can be attained by incorporating and acknowledging social, economic, and environmental concerns at every stage of the decision-making process (Mensah & Casadevall, 2019). It involves striking a balance between these issues to make sure that development satisfies current demands without endangering the environment or depleting resources for future generations. This doctrine catalyzes responsible management of available resources, protection of the ecosystem, and biodiversity conservation, while responding to current socioeconomic issues such as inequality, poverty, social justice among others.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are the major international framework for international cooperation today, and they are based on sustainability (International Institute for Sustainable Development, 2025). This served as the basis for the United Nations' 2015 adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), commonly referred to as the Global Goals, as a global call to action to eradicate poverty, safeguard the environment, and guarantee that everyone lives in peace and prosperity by 2030 (United Nations Development Programme, 2025). Academic discourse on sustainability has encompassed a wide variety of viewpoints. Economic analysts have discussed how to preserve the capital endowments required to support those income flows and have occasionally described the idea in terms of long-term economic growth or non-declining per capita income flows with negligible environmental effects. Proponents of weak and strong sustainability are split on the issue of the substitutability of natural and human-made capital; the former contend that the two forms of capital are essentially interchangeable, while the latter maintain that natural capital is becoming the scarcest factor of production (Meadowcroft, 2025). Sustainability has typically been approached by ecologists and system theorists in terms of population dynamics, energy flows, and physical interdependencies. They have focused on design elements like robustness, resiliency, redundancy, and flexibility that are appropriate for social systems to survive over the long term. Additionally, political analysts have concentrated on the public policy consequences, the nature of green political initiatives, and the ideological and moral ramifications of sustainability (Meadowcroft, 2025).

Understanding mathematics literacy for sustainable development

The study of mathematics is rational and related to science. The study of number, space, shape, and amount, as well as how they connect to one another using specialized notation, is the main focus of mathematics, which is a collection of allied sciences that includes geometry, calculus, and algebra. Many scientists, both experienced and novice, have found mathematics to be a great way to use their skills and abilities. It is a brain-thinking activity that aims to solve human issues (Azenda et al., 2023). In order to explore measurement, relationships, and the characteristics of quantities and sets, mathematics makes use of numbers and symbols. Calculus, geometry, algebra, and arithmetic are among the areas of mathematics. Equations, functions, geometric shapes, numbers, and their relationships are all studied in mathematics (Timothy, et al., 2021; Ogunode, 2020).

The cornerstone of contemporary development and the basis of science is mathematics. It is often known that a nation's degree of social and economic growth is closely linked to its level of scientific and technological advancement. The amount of social and economic progress is intimately linked to the level of advancement in the mathematical sciences because mathematics is recognized as the cornerstone of both science and technology (Richard et al., 2024). The industrial revolution caused a massive increase in the number of people living in cities during the 18th and 19th centuries. From a young age, mathematics became a major component of the curriculum in educational institutions. By the twentieth century, mathematics education became the practice of teaching and learning with associated scholarly research in contemporary education. Mathematics is part of the core curriculum in all the developed countries (Richard, et al., 2024).

Efforts to instill the value of character, skills, attitudes, and knowledge through the application of mathematics learning in the fields of environment, social, cultural, and economy are known as mathematics education for sustainable development.

This seeks to enhance the significance and use of mathematics education while fostering the growth of critical thinking, creativity, communication, and teamwork skills necessary for the twenty-first century. It is anticipated that students would use these competences as a guide in their future lives since they may all be cultivated in mathematics classes through problems presented as applications in the social, economic, and environmental domains.

According to Widiati and Juandi (2019), sustainable education must have a long-term vision that will undoubtedly be useful in the future. Therefore, sustainable mathematics education is in line with the current Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations, which include: no poverty, zero hunger, good health and well-being, quality education, gender equality, clear water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, decent work and economic growth, industry, innovation, and infrastructure, reduced inequalities, sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate action, life below water, life on land, peace, justice, and strong institutions, and partnership for the goals.

Parenting Education and Children's Early Mathematics Literacy Skills

Incorporating mathematics literacy into parental education programs would enhance children's mathematical proficiency through parent-child interactions while also promoting sustainable development practices. The findings of Wang & Wei's (2024) meta-analysis on the impact of parental participation on children's arithmetic performance, as well as their moderators, supported this. The findings demonstrated that students' arithmetic proficiency was much improved by parental participation. Participant, involvement type, grade level, geographic location, and evaluation content were all found to have moderating effects in the moderating variables study. Therefore, a key component of raising children's mathematical proficiency is including mathematics literacy into parenting education programs. Similarly, Douglas & Rittle-Johnson (2024) found that parents' knowledge of early numeracy development was positively correlated with the majority of their child-specific numeracy beliefs, but that their knowledge did not predict their reported numeracy support, while their child-specific numeracy beliefs did. Education, income, and work position did not consistently correlate with parents' understanding of early numeracy and repeating patterns development; rather, education and employment status were unique predictors of their ability to help their children in numeracy and repeating patterning. These conclusions were reached when they used a linear multiple regression analysis to examine the impact of parental knowledge on children's early math development. These results further support the idea that parents have an impact on their children's mathematical abilities, hence parenting education should focus on mathematics literacy.

In line with the findings of Cui et al. (2019), the aforementioned findings from a plethora of studies highlight the significance of parents' views toward education and their involvement in their kids' arithmetic activities. They underlined how important family education is and how the public should be fully informed about it through parenting education programs. The government should also help parents participate more in early learning activities at home. This was shown in the study by Cui et al. (2019) on how parental attitudes toward education and educational involvement behavior in early infancy can improve children's proficiency in mathematics in the fourth grade by influencing their learning interests. The study was conducted in Singapore and Hong Kong which share similar cultural backgrounds, and students demonstrating outstanding mathematical performance were selected for the study.

Parenting Education Programs On Mathematics and Sustainability Concepts

Since parents are known to have an impact on the education of the children in their care, it is essential to incorporate mathematics into parental education programs in order to help kids become more proficient in the subject. In the same way, incorporating sustainability ideas into parenting education programs would help kids learn about sustainable development, which would guarantee a sustainable future. Ghazali et al. (2021) found that while parents' attitudes and experience in mathematics were moderate, their knowledge, comprehension, and attitude toward preschoolers' numeracy were high. According to the report, parents require a pertinent manual in order to assist their kids in learning at home through efficient teaching techniques. Thus, in integrating mathematics into parenting education, sustainability concepts should be included as Ghazali, et al., (2021) found out parents attitudes towards mathematics for pre-schoolers is positive.

According to Sihvonen et al. (2024), a qualitative study examining an environmental recycling project in a Finnish kindergarten group found that socio-cultural contexts, such as the emphasis on unstructured play in natural environments and the encouragement of exploration under careful supervision, would promote sustainable behaviors in kids. Additionally, parents' significant environmental sensitivity was demonstrated by their desire to get involved in the community to support sustainability. The findings highlight how crucial it is for parents and teachers to work together to foster environmental consciousness in children at a young age. This further supports the idea that it would be crucial to incorporate sustainability principles into parenting education programs that focus on mathematics. In order to improve student accomplishment

toward sustainable living and habits, Al-Hail et al. (2021) examine the needs, problems, and current methods of parental participation in Qatari public schools. The findings suggest that there are several sorts of parental participation techniques in Qatari public schools, including both home-based and school based learning.

Additionally, it demonstrated that nearly all parents value parental participation and are very interested in serving on school boards of trustees (BoT). The majority of parents say that in order to boost their involvement, there needs to be more flexibility in the way they communicate with the school. Hence, from the expressions of parents in being part of their children education, sustainability concept could be integrated into parenting education programmes such as Parent Teachers Association (PTA) forums and others. This would improve children sustainability practices as parents maintain such concepts at home. The study was in confines of a qualitative study method. The significance of teacher-parent collaborations in fostering long-term learning results and kids' wellbeing was also emphasized by Lunga's (2024) findings. Additionally, he discovered that these collaborations foster congruence between the school culture and community needs, improve communication and decision-making, and serve as a foundation for altering parents' attitudes toward early childhood development education. The study came to the conclusion that early on in a child's education, parents and instructors should collaborate. The fact that parents still want to be involved in their kids' education suggests that they would accept the ideas of sustainable development that are taught in parenting education programs. Additionally, it would encourage youngsters to think and act in a sustainable manner both at home and at school.

Barriers To Parents And Teachers In Teaching Mathematics In View of Sustainability

According to Vásquez et al. (2023), mathematics education is a successful way to provide education that is focused on sustainability, but parents and teachers still have little information and resistive attitudes. Given that parents have a significant impact on their children's mathematical abilities and other skills, it is imperative that parenting education programs incorporate both sustainability and mathematics. The study conducted by Jay et al. (2018) in primary schools in the southwest region of England revealed certain particular drawbacks of school-centered approaches. Additionally, they suggested that school-centered methods can actually limit parents' comprehension of how to encourage arithmetic instruction at home.

Teachers' voices from around the world reveal several common barriers to multidisciplinary, learner-centered education for sustainability, including disciplinary silos, a focus on high stakes assessments, and insufficient professional learning opportunities for aspiring and practicing educators, according to Parry & Metzger (2023), despite significant context-based differences in how sustainability education is implemented. They added that these obstacles still exist in spite of repeated requests from researchers and policymakers to better prepare and assist teachers in their role as facilitators of learning for sustainability, highlighting then necessity of establishing a closer link between top-down Education for Sustainable Development policy and the needs of teachers and classroom experiences.

Conclusion

This study added to the body of knowledge by examining the relationship between parenting education, sustainable development, and mathematics literacy through a review of previous research. It came to the conclusion that parents had an impact on their children's early mathematical abilities. As a result, parenting education programs must to incorporate mathematical instruction. Additionally, based on reviewed literature, parents showed a strong desire to participate in their children's education. For this reason, when integrating mathematics education into parenting education programs, it should be done with sustainable growth in mind. As these ideas should be considered and applied in schools and at home, this would instill in kids the idea of sustainable practices. Also, in light of sustainability, parents and educators face difficulties and obstacles when it comes to teaching mathematics. Limited information, unsupportive attitudes, and school policies about sustainability and education are a few of the obstacles that have been discovered from the examined literature.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing conclusion,

1. It is necessary to incorporate mathematics into parenting education programmes in view of sustainable development in order to better prepare them in assisting their children at home.
2. Promotional materials on mathematics education should also be made available to parents to better inform them of the significance of mathematics education and their attitude towards it.
3. School administrators should also formulate and implement policies in support of parenting education in view of sustainable development through the practice of mathematics.

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